

Non-halogenated volatile solid additives for efficient organic solar cells

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Abstract

Additives can improve the performance and stability of organic solar cells (OSCs) through optimised active layer (AL) morphology. The main advantage of volatile solid additives (VSAs) compared to solvent additives is their pronounced volatility allowing for a complete removal by simple post-treatments such as thermal annealing. Halogenated VSAs resulting in very efficient devices have been studied in detail [1]. However, there is no evidence that halogenation is essential for high device performance and thus more environmentally friendly alternatives namely non-halogenated VSAs could represent viable alternatives [2].

Herein, two novel non-halogenated VSAs 1,4-diacetylbenzene (DAB) and terephthalaldehyde (TPA) (see figure below) effectively improve the power conversion efficiency (PCE) to 18.0% and 17.5%, respectively. This is a large improvement when compared to the reference binary OSC achieving a PCE of 16.9%. Furthermore, both novel VSAs improve the OSCs' stability. After >165 days of storage, the best device treated by TPA still maintains ~95% of its initial PCE compared to the reference keeping ~89% of its initial PCE. To elucidate the working mechanisms we combined photoluminescence, X-ray scattering and nanoscale imaging techniques, allowing us to investigate the synergistic effects of the VSAs and the annealing temperature. These findings demonstrate the broad prospects of non-halogenated VSAs in the fabrication of highly efficient organic semiconductors.

References

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Figure: Schematic of the AL morphology reorganization upon the use of a non-halogenated VSA